

DESIGN OF A CRASHWORTHY LANDING GEAR USING COMPOSITE TUBE

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SUMMARY

Landing gear is the one of major components to achieve aircraft's crashworthiness. The concept of crashworthy landing gear, which absorbs extra energy using a failure of composite tube, is presented. The performance is investigated by dynamic simulation, showing that energy absorbing capability can be improved by crush tube in crash case.

Keywords: Landing gear, Crashworthiness, Composite tube, Energy absorption

INTRODUCTION

The main function of a landing gear is to absorb the impact energy during touchdown. It can also have crashworthiness by limiting the peak load and absorbing the energy together with airframe in crash case. The crashworthy requirement and various design concepts are available in the literature[1-2]. Most landing gear absorbs the impact energy using an oleo-pneumatic shock absorber which essentially consists of an oil damper and a gas spring. An oil flow through an orifice builds up a high back pressure which can react against the moving piston and hence provide high resistance to motion. This creates the damper. The damper is ineffective at low speed since it is the rate of flow which creates the back pressure (the pressure drop being proportional to the square of the speed). To overcome this, the device has a gas spring which experiences a polytropic process as it expands and contracts.

The damping orifice is designed to have best efficiency for normal landing environments because it is the case that landing gear experiences mostly during all usage life. Thus it can be inefficient when landing gear is subjected to much higher sink speed than normal landing speed. The damping force can be extremely high and a big load might be transmitted to airframe. If airframe structure is not strong enough, then the landing gear can penetrate into crew seat and cause a fatal injury. To prevent this, landing gear is required to have crashworthiness by adapting additional device.

This paper presents the crash device using a failure of composite materials in order to increase energy absorption ability. To do so, the impact behaviour of composite tube is analyzed and shock absorbing capability is investigated. And then total energy absorption by oleo-pneumatic shock absorber and composite tube is predicted and compared with ordinary shock absorber. The peak loads, which are caused by high damping or shock strut bottoming, could be significantly reduced by introducing composite tube in crash case. The introduction of composite tube can be a good solution to a crashworthy landing gear.

CONCEPT OF CRASH DEVICE

For helicopter landing gears, one of the solutions for crashworthy design is a mechanical device for additional energy absorption. It is installed coaxially to the shock absorber and does not any functions in normal landing conditions. In case of crash landing, it begins to crush and absorb the impact energy. The basic structure of landing gear is depicted in Figure 1. The assembly is basically composed of four components, which are the cylinder, the piston, the main fitting connecting landing gear with airframe and the composite tube for additional energy absorption. This composite tube is easily tailored to achieve desired mechanical characteristics. In normal landing conditions, the shock strut, composed of piston and cylinder, absorbs the impact energy. And the ground loads are transmitted to airframe structure through main fitting. Under crash condition, the high impact force cause the failure of shear pin, which in turn allows the cylinder to slide inside the main fitting. This frangible shear pin is designed to fail at a given load and act as a trigger to activate crash tube. Then the crash tube begins to fail and absorb the energy.

Figure 1. Crash device using composite tube.

PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

Crash tube

The finite element analysis is performed to investigate the energy absorbing characteristics of composite tube. The LS-DYNA, explicit FE code, is used for simulation. The geometry and FE mesh of crash tube can be represented as in Figure 2. The main fitting is represented as the moving platen and the crash tube is fixed on stationary base. The moving platen and the base are regarded as rigid bodies. The composite tube is considered as the transversely isotropic material, whose mechanical properties are shown in Table 1.

Figure 2 The geometry and FE mesh of crash tube.

The boundary condition of the moving platen is a constant velocity of 10m/s along the z axis. This velocity can be determined by the stroke rate from landing gear drop simulation. Except the z directional displacement, all other displacements and rotations are fixed. The result plot is Figure 3 which shows force versus composite tube shortening length.

Table 1 Material properties of crash tube

E_{11} (GPa)	E_{22} (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	G_{23} (GPa)	γ_{12}
230	40	24	14.3	0.25

Figure 3 Impact analysis of composite tube.

Landing gear drop simulation

First, the performance of landing gear without crash tube is simulated by commercial software, VI-Aircraft. Figure 4 shows the example of landing gear model. All structural members are regarded as rigid body and the impact energy is absorbed by shock absorber and tire.

Figure 4. Landing gear model for performance analysis.

The performance of a landing gear can be investigated by 'ground load versus shock absorber stroke' plot [3]. The efficiency of shock absorber is defined as

$$\eta = \frac{\text{Energy Absorbed (Area under the curve)}}{\text{Max. Load} \times \text{Max. Stroke}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

From equation (1), 100% of the efficiency can be achieved if the curve shape is rectangular, which is an ideal case. In actual use, to achieve a good efficiency, the initial and end peak loads must have similar for the curve to be shaped like a rectangle. In Figure 5, it can be known that the shock absorber efficiency becomes worse as sink speed increases. Because the orifice is generally designed for sink speeds which occur frequently, it can not show a good performance for abnormal cases. The initial peak load increases rapidly, which may cause a failure of airframe structure and a damage of crew. The end peak load also can be a problem. When the full stroke is not enough for energy absorption in emergency, the shock absorber can be bottomed. Then metal to metal contact occurs, which produce a very big load (Figure 6). The load is transferred into the airframe which might not sustain the excessive load. Thus, the additional shock absorbing device might be necessary in case of emergency to limit the load increase and human safety.

Figure 5 The peak load increase with varying sink speeds

Figure 6 The end peak load increase by S/A bottoming

Introduction of crash tube

After the shock absorber bottomed (piston touches the cylinder head so no more stroke is available for energy absorption), the crash tube begins to absorb the energy by crushing. This contribution is superposed on the original energy curve. From the designated stroke, the energy absorption by crash tube is added to the original energy curve by shock absorber. Though two models are separately analyzed which might not represent the realistic situation, it is enough to investigate overall performance. From

Figure 7, the peak load transmitted to airframe can be efficiently controlled by the failure of crash tube. When only shock absorber used, the end peak load becomes very large because of bottoming. By introducing crash tube, the peak load could be limited and more energy is absorbed by landing gear. Thus shock absorbing efficiency and the safety of crew can be improved.

Figure 7 Comparison of energy absorbing behaviors

CONCLUSION

To absorb the additional energy in case of emergency, the composite crash tube can be a good solution. It reduces the peak load resulting from very high sink speed, which prevents load transferring to the airframe and human injuries. For the future work, the revised numerical model, where landing gear and crash tube are integrated together, is now being developed to obtain more realistic results. Also, the drop test is to be conducted in order to prove the mathematical model and apply the composite tube to actual use.

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